

Assessment on Impact of Social-Media-Platforms on Examination Malpractice among Secondary School Science Students in Ido/Osi Local Government Area, Ekiti State

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices among secondary school science students in Ido/Osi Local Government Area, Ekiti State. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school science students in Ido/Osi Local Government Area of Ekiti State during the 2023/2024 academic session. 200 students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique from the targeted population. Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. A well-developed questionnaire was used to obtain information from the respondents. The reliability of the instrument was obtained with test-retest approach using Pearson product moment correlation and the reliability coefficient was 0.85. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency count, percentage and mean). Findings revealed that, secondary school science students have varied perceptions on the impact of social media on examination malpractices regarding their awareness, beliefs and personal experiences. Findings further reveal that social media platforms contributed to prevalent of examination malpractices such as cheating, collusion, stealing, impersonation, alteration, and disorderliness of candidate at examination hall in secondary schools. Study revealed that, the commonly used social platforms among students are Whatsapp, Instagram, Telegram, X and Facebook. In conclusion, the study revealed a diverse spectrum of perceptions among secondary school science students concerning the influence of social media on examination malpractices. Among others, it was recommended that, school management should develop and implement educational campaigns targeted at raising awareness among secondary school science students about the ethical implications and consequences of engaging in examination malpractices through social media platforms.

Keywords: Social Media, Examination Malpractices, Perceptions, Science Students

Introduction

Examination Malpractices encompass a wide range of improper behaviours carried out by students during examination aiming to manipulate their examination scores or deceive evaluators. These malpractices could include bringing unauthorized electronic devices into the examination hall, collusion or collaboration among students to show answers, impersonation, or altering examinations scripts (Nkwo, Mboto & Akinbobola, 2006). These actions undermine the fairness and credibility of assessments. Characteristics of examination malpractice students include: students being unstable, mobile and highly tensed, anxiety, fears, un fanatic movement and unsteady eyeballs that portray them as potential cheats; unusual movements of parents, mercenaries and unauthorized persons around the examination premises may signal some warnings; unusual attachment to each other as in talking and intimately walking together prior examinations may indicate the tendency for irregularities, inordinate financial bribe examination personnel; unusual wear of over-sized dresses with large number of pockets to conceal foreign materials; wearing of very short skirts by girls to enable them easily read notes and formulae written on their thighs, laps, handkerchiefs, currency notes, and possibly smartphones with which answers to leak examination questions may be communicated (Denga & Denga, 1998 cited in Nkwo, Mboto & Akinbobola, 2006). Acai & Lee (2019) define examination malpractices as the examinations not conduct in accordance with specified norms set up by the examining institution or body. Nkwo, Mboto and Akinbobola (2006). state that, examination malpractices involves the various methods employed by candidates to cheat before or during examination.

With the advent of advanced technologies and increased access to the internet, students have more opportunities to engage in dishonest behaviours during examinations. Students resort to various tactics such as using smartphones to access unauthorized information, sharing answers through science messaging apps, and collaborating during online science subjects examinations (Akinbobola, 2019).

The ease of communication and access to information via digital science platforms has made imperative for educational institutions to implement robust strategies to detect and prevent examination malpractices (Brown & Lee, 2019).

The impact of examination malpractices extends beyond the immediate context affecting the credibility of educational systems and diminishing the value of academic qualifications. It was observed that, students generally have difficulty in understanding mathematics and science subject's curriculum and this perhaps account for their consistent examination malpractices in the subjects in Senior School Certificates Examination (Ado, Akinbobola & Ugbe, 2006). Most students find science, especially mathematics difficult and unpalatable due to false impression about the difficulties in science subjects and the perhaps account for the reasons why students embark on cheating during examinations (Ado, Akinbobola & Inyang, 2006). Ezekannagha (2000) observed that, many Nigerian students see science subjects they study in schools as abstract, involving symbols and formulae. Ezekannagha explained further that, the students lack the ability to appreciate concepts taught in school and their relevance in the explanation of things and activities within environment. To tackle the issue of examination malpractices effectively, it is essential to understand the underlying psychological factors that drive students to cheat.

Fear of failure, intense competition, and pressure to achieve high grades has been identified as key motivators for academic dishonesty (Johnson, 2019). Moreover, a study by Wang, Chen and Li (2019) found that, cultural factors for academic success can contribute significantly to cheating behaviour among students. Technological advancement offers both challenges and opportunities in combating examination malpractices, while technology facilitates cheating in science, it also provides potential solutions. Anti – cheating science software on examination platforms have emerged as tools to detect and defer cheating attempt (Miller, Turner & Simmons, 2019).

In recent years, social media has become an integrated part of modern society providing an interconnected platform for communication and information sharing and also facilitate academic dishonesty particularly during science examination. Social media platforms enable students to share and exchange examination related materials, such as leaked question paper solutions to ongoing science examination. This ease of access to confidential information raises concerns about the integrity of examinations (Johnson,2018). For example, an investigation in India found that the WhatsApp groups were being used to distribute leaked examination papers, leading to widespread cheating (BBC News, 2017).

Social media allow students to communicate in real-time regardless of geographical locations (Akinbobola & Asagha, 2015). During examination, this facilitates instant exchange of information, enabling students to share scientific formulae, answers and ask for help discreetly. Platforms like Facebook, Messenger or direct messages on twitter are difficult to monitor, making it challenging for educational institutions to direct cheating incidents promptly (Severance, Cikijewskic & Yen, 2019). Various social media group forums have emerged where students can seek and provide assistance with science examination preparation while some groups foster healthy discussions and knowledge sharing, others may transform into scientific platforms for examination cheating. Science students might request or receive detailed answers to examination questions, undermining the assessments fairness and academic standard (Folthynek & Kralik, 2020)

With advancement in technology of social media platforms, the integration of social media into institution of learning makes detection even more challenging (Salman, Shalan, Mahmood, & Khan, 2020). Social media also provides a platform for essay mills and contract cheating services to advertise their offerings, connecting students with third- party individuals willing to complete assignments and examinations on their behalf (Lancaster & Cotarlan, 2018). These services exploit the anonymity of social media to operate covertly, further complicating the efforts to combat academic dishonesty. Social media undoubtedly plays a significant role in facilitating cheating during examination among science students. It ease to access real-time communication, and wide-ranging connections make it an attractive avenue for dishonest practices.

Examination malpractices among secondary school science students have become prevalent, and it is essential to understand students' perceptions regarding the impact of social media platforms on this issue. Social media has rapidly gained popularity among science students and there is a need to investigate how these platforms contribute to, enable or facilitate examination malpractices. By exploring student's perspectives on the relationship between social media and examination malpractices, this study aimed to provide valuable insights into the role and influence of these platforms in promoting unethical conduct during examinations among secondary school science students. Understanding these perceptions is crucial for developing effective measures, interventions and policies to mitigate the negative impact of social media on academic integrity.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the student's perceptions on the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices among secondary school science students. Specifically, the study tends;

1. To investigate the level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices.
2. To investigate the types of examination malpractices that are prevalent among secondary school students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices

3. To identify the different social media platforms that is commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices.

Research Questions

Three research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the level of awareness among the secondary school science students about the impact social media platforms on examination malpractices?
2. What are the type of examination malpractices that are prevalent among secondary school science students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices?
3. What are the different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of this study consisted all senior secondary school science students of Ido/Osi Local Government Area, Ekiti State, Nigeria. Multistage sampling technique was used for the study. Five co-educational schools were selected through simple random technique. Forty (40) students each was chosen from five randomly selected secondary schools in Ido/Osi Local Government Area of Ekiti State.

The research instrument used for collection of data was a self- constructed questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into 2 Section; Section A and B. Section A consisted of information on bio-data of the respondents while the Section B was divided into parts with items from each part addressing the stated research questions. A 4 –point Likert type rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA)= 4, Agree (A)=3. Disagree (D)=2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1 was used. Each of the respondent picked the items as applicable. The research instrument was validated using face and content validity with the help of two (2) experts in the test, measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was obtained with test-retest approach using Pearson product moment correlation and the reliability coefficient was 0.85. The researcher took permission from the principals and through them, got in touch with the science teachers and students in the schools for the administration of the questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using frequency count, percentage and mean.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices?

Table 1: The level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices

S/N	Level of Awareness	SA	A	D	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	I have been educated about the negative effect of social media on examination malpractices	60 (30.0)	76 (38.0)	36 (18.0)	28 (14.0)	2.84	Accepted
2	I think most students are aware of how social media can lead to examination malpractices	79 (39.5)	54 (27.0)	45 (22.5)	22 (11.0)	2.95	Accepted
3	I feel well informed regarding the impact of social media on examination cheating	44 (22.0)	69 (34.5)	41 (20.5)	46 (23.0)	2.56	Accepted
4	I pay attention to information about the relationship between social media and examination malpractices	68 (34.0)	65 (32.5)	33 (16.5)	34 (17.0)	2.84	Accepted
5	I have personally witness or experienced examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms	78 (39.0)	48 (24.0)	48 (24.0)	26 (13.0)	2.89	Accepted

Weighted Average = 2.82; Benchmark = 2.50

Table 1 shows the level of awareness among secondary school science students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices. The table shows that, most science students (68.0%) have been educated about negative effect of

social media on examination malpractices (2.84). Also, some of the respondents (66.5%) pay attention to the information about the relationship between social media and examination malpractices (2.95). The table also shows that, some of the respondents (56.5% are well-informed regarding the impact of social media on examination cheating (2.56). The table also shows that, most students (66.5%) are aware of how the use of social media can lead to examination malpractices (2.95). Also, most students (63%) personally witness or experienced examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms (2.89). Since the weighted average of 2.82 as shown in Table 1 is greater than the benchmark of 2.50, it can be concluded that, level of awareness among secondary school students about the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices is high, that is, they perceived the impact of social media on examination malpractices.

Research Question 2

What are the type of examination malpractices that are prevalent among secondary school science students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices?

Table 2: The type of examination malpractices that is prevalent among secondary school students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to these malpractices

S/N	Prevalent Examination Malpractices	SA	A	D	SD	Mean $\bar{(x)}$	Decision
1	Cheating in examination is common among science students in my school	61 (30.5)	57 (28.5)	65 (32.9)	17 (8.50)	2.81	Accepted
2	I belief that social media platforms are major contributor to examination malpractices	61 (30.0)	102 (51.0)	32 (16.0)	6 (3.0)	3.08	Accepted
3	Students in my school often use social media to share examination related information	83 (41.5)	64 (32)	38 (19)	15 (7.5)	3.08	Accepted
4	Social media make it easier for students to engage in cheating during examination	90 (45)	83 (41.5)	18 (9.0)	9 (4.5)	3.27	Accepted
	Weighted Average					3.06	

Benchmark = 2.50

Table 2 shows the perception on types of examination malpractices that is prevalent among secondary school students and the extent to which social media platforms contribute to the practices. The table shows that, cheating in examinations is common among science students (2.81); social media platforms are the major contributor to examination malpractices (3.08); the science students in school often use social media to share examination related information (3.08); and social media makes it easier for students to engage in cheating during examinations (3.27). Meanwhile, since the weighted average as shown in Table 3 is 3.06 which is greater than the benchmark of 2.50, it can be concluded that, social media platform is the type of examination malpractices that is prevalent among secondary school science students.

Research Question 3

What are the different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices?

Table 3: The different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices

S/N	Commonly Used Social Media Platforms	SA	A	D	SD	Mean $\bar{(x)}$	Decision
1	Students often use WhatsApp for sharing examination related content	118 (59.0)	56 (28.0)	3 (1.5)	23 (11.5)	3.35	Accepted
2	Facebook is commonly used for cheating during examinations	60 (30.0)	49 (24.5)	32 (16.0)	59 (29.5)	2.55	Accepted
3	Instagram is a popular platform for examination malpractices	51 (25.5)	74 (37.0)	37 (18.5)	38 (19.0)	2.69	Accepted

4	I have observed students using telegram sharing examination answers	45 (22.5)	87 (43.5)	51 (25.5)	17 (8.5)	2.80	Accepted
5	Twitter is frequently used by students for discussing examination	50 (25.0)	69 (34.5)	46 (23.0)	35 (34.50)	2.67 (17.5)	Accepted

Weighted Average = 2.81; Benchmark = 2.50

Table 3 shows the perception of students on different social media platforms that are commonly used by secondary school science students. The table shows that, majority of the respondents agreed that, WhatsApp is most widely used platforms for sharing examination related content among secondary school science students (3.35). Also, Facebook is commonly used for cheating (2.55), Instagram is a popular platform used for examination malpractices (2.69), and Telegram is also good for sharing examination answers (2.80). Some of the respondents also indicate that, students frequently use twitter (2.67). Meanwhile, since the weighted average shown in the Table 3 is 2.81 which is greater than the benchmark of 2.50, it can therefore be concluded that, different social media platforms are commonly used by secondary school science students for engaging in examination malpractices.

Discussion

Findings from research questions revealed that, some science students have been educated about the negative effects of social media on examination malpractices. This is in agreement with the findings of Bown and Lee (2019), and Akinbobola (2019) that, the case of communication and access to information via digital science platforms has made imperative for educational institutions to implement robust strategies to detect and prevent examination malpractices. Also, the impact of examination malpractices extends beyond the immediate context affecting the credibility of educational systems and diminishing the value of academic qualifications. The findings indicate a mixed landscape of understanding and perception among the students. A notable percentage of students express awareness and concern about the negative effects of social media in the context of examination integrity (Johnson, 2019; Severance Cikijewskic & Yen, 2019). provides a detailed overview that platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram and Twitter are being actively used by students for activities that compromise the fairness and credibility of examinations. However, it also important to acknowledge that, there are some students who either disagree with or strongly disagree with statements related to their education and personal experiences with examination malpractices facilitated by social media. This divergence in opinions and experiences heights the need for a comprehensive and uniform approach for educating students about the risks and consequences of using social media for noticed purpose during examinations.

Conclusion

The study reveals a diverse spectrum of perceptions among secondary school science students concerning the influence of social media on examination malpractices. A notable portion of respondents exhibit strong agreement regarding the prevalence of cheating, collusion, stealing, impersonation, leakage and alteration, and the impact of social media platforms on examination malpractices among secondary school science students. WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram and Twitter emerge as prominent platforms utilized for such malpractices, highlighting the multifaceted nature of students' engagement in unethical behaviours. These findings underscore the pressing need for proactive measures and educational interventions to address the concerns surrounding secondary school science students' involvement in examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. School management should develop and implement educational campaigns targeted at raising awareness among secondary school science students about the ethical implications and consequences of engaging in examination malpractices through social media platforms.
2. Government should integrate digital literacy programmes into the secondary school curriculum to empower students with the necessary skills and knowledge to critically evaluate and responsible navigate social media platforms.
3. School management and the teachers should promote a culture of academic integrity and ethical conduct within secondary schools through the establishment of clear policies and guidelines governing student's behaviour during examinations.

4. School management should collaborate with parents, guardians and the wider community to reinforce the importance of ethical behaviour and responsible use of social media among secondary school science students.
5. School management should explore alternative assessment methods that will reduce the susceptibility of examination malpractices facilitated by social media platforms.

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